

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH
AND MODELLING

D6.8 Synthesis and lessons learnt on community and citizen responses and impacts – Update M36

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Executive Summary

The present deliverable synthesizes the findings in COVINFORM work package 6, which focuses on citizen and community impacts and responses. Whereas the prior iteration (D6.4) was based on desk research and interviews with representatives of civil society organisations in ten target municipalities, this iteration also draws on the findings of interviews with low-socioeconomic-status women living in these municipalities. It addresses the research questions identified in previous deliverables (e.g., D6.6), integrating findings from both stakeholder and resident perspectives. It then derives lessons learned that are relevant to policy and practice, for instance:

- Pre-existing spatial inequalities such as overcrowded housing, digital divides, and poor infrastructure multiplied the threat of COVID-19 and the repercussions of pandemic measures. CSOs attempted to break this cycle by offering localised (on-site and mobile) services, but were often overwhelmed, and sometimes lacked resources or coordination support.
- Residents' localised and digital social networks channelled both socio-psychological and material support, especially for groups with limited exposure to formal social welfare systems. Social networks were also pathways for secondary crisis communication – which sometimes helped fill information gaps, but also heightened exposure to misinformation.
- Both CSOs and residents played a role in local multi-stakeholder responses. CSOs often filled gaps in governmental responses, including by mitigating their unintended consequences. Residents both volunteered with CSOs and self-organised to offer mutual aid. Such bottom-up participatory practices augmented resilience in the target sites.
- Clusters of shared attitudes and behaviours emerged regarding the pandemic and response measures, which can be broadly categorised as 'mainstream' (tendency to trust/compliance) and 'rejectionist' (tendency to distrust/non-compliance). Most residents fell in between these extremes. 'Rejectionism' is individual and complex, and bursting the 'rejectionist' filter bubble would require two-way dialogue rather than just one-way messaging.
- The pandemic exacerbated existing ethnic and socioeconomic inequalities, as well as giving rise to new modalities of discrimination. However, it also catalysed spontaneous expressions of cohesion and solidarity, from which policymakers and CSOs should try to learn.

The triangulation of data sources opens a constructively critical perspective on the COVINFORM risk assessment model. Key lessons learned are that vulnerable populations do not always perceive or prioritise threats in the same way as authorities; individual and systemic vulnerabilities are most often experienced as multidimensional (e.g., not only health-related, social, or economic, but all three); and resilience must be cultivated through bottom-up participatory practices as well as top-down policy interventions. Finally, the data triangulation deepens our understanding of the social-ecological systems framework as a tool for crisis management and communication.

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
CSO	Civil society organisation
RQ	Research question
SESF	Social-ecological systems framework

1 Introduction

On a project level, COVINFORM addresses the following research questions:

- **RQ1:** How and under which conditions were COVID-19 responses drafted and practiced?
- **RQ2:** How and in which ways was vulnerability considered in COVID-19 response?
- **RQ3:** What were lived experiences of the pandemic and its response within certain vulnerable groups?
- **RQ4:** What were the different kinds of barriers encountered in the pandemic response and how were they managed?
- **RQ5:** What are the lessons learned and promising practices that can be identified in COVID-19 responses across diverse local contexts?

Within the project, work package 6 adopts a civil society perspective on these questions. Its key aims are to describe local community structures and stakeholder networks, local implementations and impacts of governmental responses, and voluntary and citizen-led responses in selected sub-national sites in the 15 project target countries. Based on desk research and a review of the scientific literature on “community”, WP6-specific corollaries to RQ5 were developed (D6.2, pg. 28-30; D6.6, pg. 6-7):

- **RQ5.1. Location:** How did spatial system conditions and spatialised practices mediate COVID-19 impacts and responses in the sub-national research sites?
- **RQ5.2. Social ties:** How did social networks mediate COVID-19 impacts in the sub-national research sites?
- **RQ5.3. Joint action:** What roles have CSOs, grassroots initiatives, and residents played in the provision of health and social services in the sub-national research sites?
- **RQ5.4. Shared attitudes and practices:** How did shared attitudes, beliefs, and practices mediate COVID-19 impacts in the sub-national research sites?
- **RQ5.5. Intra-community diversity:** How did intra-community patterns of difference mediate COVID-19 impacts in the sub-national research sites?

This deliverable addresses these research questions via a triangulation of desk research findings and qualitative data collected from CSO representatives (N=50) and residents (N=120) within ten European municipalities. It then assesses the relevance of the findings to the theoretical models used in the project as a whole: the COVINFORM risk assessment model and the social-ecological systems framework (SESF).

2 Background

2.1 Desk research

The first phase of WP6 (T6.1), conducted in Q3 2020, entailed desk research on COVID-19 responses on a sub-national level in the 15 COVINFORM target countries. The scope of the sub-national unit chosen per country varied (NUTS2, NUTS3, or LAU), but generally comprised “municipalities”, broadly defined. Relevant primary sources and secondary documentary sources (scholarly studies, grey literature, etc.) were both reviewed. The resultant report (D6.1) was a set of country reports, followed by a comparative analysis of success factors in multi-level governance. These included transparent organisation, solidarity with residents, coordination between stakeholder groups, effective use and promotion of technology, respect for diversity, and door-to-door presence and action.

A second round of desk research was conducted in Q3 2022, focusing specifically on participatory practices, i.e., practices in which ‘ordinary people’ played an active and substantial role. The resultant report (D6.5) identified over N=150 participatory practices were identified, including examples initiated by self-organised groups of residents, CSOs, public authorities, or any combination of these and/or other actors. These practices achieved a range of positive outcomes: they addressed critical needs during periods of systemic stress; offered supplements or alternatives to governmental services, especially for groups with low trust in government; reduced barriers to support; and helped mitigate the negative consequences of disruptive policies such as lockdowns.

2.2 Empirical research

The second phase of WP6 (T6.2 and T6.3) entailed empirical research in sub-national sites in 10 selected countries. In order to develop theory-driven research questions and data collection instruments, a review was conducted of scientific definitions of “community”, which have been the subject of debate since the late 19th century. A shortcoming of most scientific definitions is that they are formulated deductively rather than inductively. An exception is MacQueen et al. (2001), who sought to investigate the way members of vulnerable populations themselves understood “community”. Within the context of a 1995-1998 United States study on HIV vaccine trials, MacQueen et al. asked members of particular vulnerable populations the open question, “what does community mean to you?”. Responses were double-coded and analysed using a form of cluster analysis, which revealed five elements that typify vulnerable groups’ experiences of geographically-situated and non-geographically-situated communities:

- Locus (spatial factors)
- Social ties (relationships)
- Joint action (actions taken together or in coordination with others)
- Sharing (shared attributes, behaviours, resources, etc.)
- Diversity (intra-community differences and their effects)

A review of prior research confirmed that all five of these elements have impacted COVID-19 outcomes worldwide. Furthermore, it was theorised that these elements could complement the social-ecological systems framework (SESF) utilised in COVINFORM WP39 (see D6.2, Annex 1). A review of the relevance of these factors is provided in COVINFORM Bi-Monthly Report 12, “A civil society organisation perspective on vulnerability: Lessons learned during COVID-19” (Edwards, 2022).

Figure 1. The elements of community (MacQueen et al., 2001; adapted in Edwards, 2022)

Accordingly, these elements were adopted as a framework for the development of data collection instruments (see D6.2, Annex 2). The data collection instruments were translated by each partner and adapted as needed to conditions in each target site.

The first round of empirical research was conducted in February through May 2022, and aimed to interview N=5 representatives of civil society organisations per target site. Due to recruiting challenges, a total of 38 interviews were conducted across nine of the ten intended target sites (76% of the target of N=50). The resultant report (D6.3) covered sites in which N≥3 interviews were achieved. Partners that did not achieve this minimum sample by the deadline continued to recruit and conduct interviews; eventually, the target sample of N=50 was met. An updated report (D6.7) covered findings from all civil society organisation interviews in all countries, as specified in the table below:

Table 1. CSO representative interviews

Site	CSO interviews prior to May 2022	CSO interviews after May 2022	CSO interviews total
Austria (Vienna)	3	2	5
Belgium (Antwerp)	3	2	5
England (Birmingham)	0	5	5
Germany (Mannheim)	5	0	5
Greece (Athens)	5	0	5
Italy (Rome)	4	1	5
Portugal (Lisbon)	5	0	5
Spain (Madrid)	5	0	5
Sweden (Gothenburg)	4	1	5
Wales (Swansea)	4	1	5

Total	N=38	N=12	N=50
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The second round of empirical research was conducted from June to September 2022, during which N=12 low-socioeconomic-status (SES) women were interviewed per target site (total N=120). The decision to focus on low-SES women was taken for several reasons:

- Low SES has been consistently identified as a risk factor for adverse outcomes not only in the economic domain, but also the health and social domains; likewise, gender was identified early on as a mediating factor in experiences of the pandemic. This is true across national contexts, making cross-national comparative analysis appropriate.
- Choosing a narrowly defined target population enabled data saturation with a comparatively small within-country sample of N=12. With regard to sample size, a balance needed to be struck between suitability for within-county vs. cross-country analysis. On the one hand, the sample per country needed to be large enough to yield meaningful findings on the target population within the target site; on the other hand, interviewing a very large sample per country would generate too large of a cross-national dataset to be comprehensively analysed within the project timeframe.
- Choosing a narrowly defined target population is also beneficial from the standpoint of actionability. Particular policies and measures are designed to support low-SES women, and particular institutions serve them. Findings on low-SES women’s experiences of the pandemic are directly relevant to the stakeholders involved.
- Throughout the project, consideration was given to both ‘ascribed vulnerability’ (being labelled as vulnerable by others or institutions) and the ‘lived experience of vulnerability’ – as well as to differences in the ways vulnerability is described from emic and etic perspectives. Focusing on a target population widely perceived as vulnerable provides the opportunity to delve into such differences.
- None of the WP3 case studies focused on this target population (though many of the case study target populations overlapped with it).

An interview topic guide was created collaboratively by the WP4, WP5, WP6, and WP7 teams, which encompassed project-level research questions and a selection of sub-questions critical to each WP. The topic guide was influenced by the model of the problem-centred interview (PCI), a theory-driven model of semi-structured interview intended to enable the research participant to describe their way of making sense of a given ‘problem’ without being unduly influenced by the researcher and her theoretical concept (Mohr 1998; Witzel 2012). In keeping with the PCI model, the topic guide began with a broad question designed to elicit an open narration: “Could you tell me about when you first realised that the COVID-19 pandemic would affect your everyday life?” Interviewers were instructed not to interrupt interviewees, but rather to wait for a natural break before introducing the second question, which was also narrative: “When you think back, could you tell me the three most important memories of the COVID-19 pandemic?” In order to ensure that sufficient data was collected on topics relevant to WP4-7, this opening narrative block was followed by a block of traditional semi-structured interview questions on the topics of social networks and support, information-seeking and sense-making, and living environments. A focus on social networks and relationships was taken because socioeconomic disadvantage often leads to social exclusion, which can in turn limit access to information or instrumental forms of support. During the pandemic, lockdown and social distancing

measures aggravated the isolation of some individuals, despite more social support being needed to cope with the stress factors surrounding finances, health, and wellbeing. It was hypothesised that low-SES women were ‘double burdened’ during the pandemic, facing greater vulnerability to the negative impacts of COVID-19 and COVID-19 response measures alike.

Recruiting was conducted through gatekeeper organisations. The inclusion criteria for potential participants were: 1) female self-identification; and 2) self-identification as a recipient of financial or material support from social welfare programmes or civil society organisations. Women who would be eligible to receive financial or material support based on their economic circumstances, but who were not receiving support due to their nationality, residence status, or other extra-economic factors (e.g., inability to navigate bureaucratic barriers, etc.) were also invited to participate. In some cases, participants were recruited directly through the organisations that provided them with financial or material support. In other cases (e.g., when social welfare institution policies did not permit such cooperation), recruiting was conducted via other civil society organisations that serve vulnerable women, using a screener. Gatekeepers were not coerced, manipulated, or unduly induced financially or otherwise to assist with recruiting.

Careful consideration was given as to how to compensate participants for any expenses they incurred, and/or for their time and intellectual labour (Fry and Dwyer 2001; Head 2009; Russell et al. 2000; Singer and Kulka 2002). This required balancing the potential of “undue inducements” to compromise the voluntariness of consent and the reliability of the data collected (European Commission Directorate-General for Research 2010, p. 38-39) against the fact that economic precarity can “[exclude certain groups] from participation in research” (ibid., p. 121). It also required acknowledging the privilege of the researcher, who is materially compensated for their own participation in the “knowledge co-production” (Fedyuk and Zentai 2018). Due to institutional constraints on some partners, the decision as to whether or not to offer financial honoraria or comparable incentives (e.g., vouchers) was made on a partner-by-partner basis. Those partners that did offer honoraria, did so in a confidential and safe manner, making it clear that they were unconditional.¹

In accordance with the COVINFORM ethics framework, a comprehensive project information sheet in simple language was provided, and potential participants were given the opportunity to ask questions about the project and the interview procedure before being asked to sign an informed consent form. Participants were given the option of conducting their interview either face-to-face or via telephone or online. In comparison to the CSO representative recruiting and fieldwork, the resident recruiting and fieldwork was comparatively smooth in all countries (undoubtedly due in part to the fact that social distancing regulations had been removed in all target sites by the fieldwork period). The fieldwork period was originally specified as June to July 2023, but was extended to September 2023. All partners met the target sample, as indicated in the below table:

¹ The use of monetary incentives in medical and psychological research, including public health research, has long been a matter of convention (Russell, Moralejo & Burgess 2000). Their use in sociological and anthropological research is less common; however, recent feminist critical scholarship has suggested, “omitting to pay participants has sometimes been characterised as unethical, so that making payments (or gift-giving) becomes a mark of ethically sound research” (Head 2009, 337). In light of these considerations, the COVINFORM consortium determines that reasonable “fair returns for assistance” are methodologically justifiable as a means of reducing possible socioeconomic barriers to participation, thereby helping to mitigate the risk of implicitly “[excluding certain groups] from participation in research and the benefits that may attach to research participation” (European Commission Directorate-General for Research and Innovation 2010, p. 121).

Table 1. Resident interviews

Site	Resident interviews
Austria (Vienna)	12
Belgium (Antwerp)	12
England (Birmingham)	12
Germany (Mannheim)	12
Greece (Athens)	12
Italy (Rome)	12
Portugal (Lisbon)	12
Spain (Madrid)	12
Sweden (Gothenburg)	12
Wales (Swansea)	12
Total	N=120

2.3 Analysis

The aim of T6.4 is to conduct an analysis of the WP6 findings with reference to the project research questions, the COVINFORM risk assessment model, and the social-ecological systems framework (SESF; McGinnis & Ostrom 2014). The first round of analysis was conducted in Q2 2022 based on the findings of CSO interview. The report (D6.4) validated the risk assessment model's categories of threats, vulnerabilities, and consequences, as well as the SESF's constituent sub-systems (governance systems, resource systems and units, actor systems, and action situations), from a CSO perspective. It also found that CSO representatives understand threats and vulnerabilities in terms that concur with the behaviours of complex adaptive systems: they are inherently multidimensional; they produce effects that cascade across the physical/health, social, economic, and informational domains; and they are mediated by local and global networks. The report concluded that CSOs can contribute to crisis responses by bridging diverse actor groups in society, and that they can most effectively do so by leveraging the aspects of social life that these groups share (e.g., locations, attitudes and behaviours, relationships, and activities), while also maintaining respect for diversity (cf. MacQueen et al. 2001; Edwards 2022).

This deliverable is the result of a second round of analysis conducted in Q3 2023, incorporating both the prior WP6 research findings and the resident interview findings. The resident interviews were recorded and transcribed by the interviewing partners; the transcripts were then pseudonymised, translated into English, and shared with the consortium via a secure folder. Coding was conducted by the WP leaders (KEMEA, UANTWERPEN, SINUS, and SYNIO) using a collaboratively-designed codebook in the software package MAXQDA. Code categories and certain key codes were defined deductively from the project-level and WP-specific research questions, while additional codes within each category were added inductively based on the transcript contents.

3 Synthesis of findings

Based on both prior studies and desk research conducted on municipal-level impacts and measures in the COVINFORM target sites, MacQueen et al.'s (2001) definitional elements of community (locus; social ties; joint action; shared attitudes and practices; diversity) were confirmed as highly relevant to the COVINFORM WP6 research aims. They were accordingly adopted as a framework for the development of the work-package-specific research questions specified in the introduction. Rather than assuming that each sub-national research site or target population constituted an *a priori* “community”, the research team explored how different dimensions of “community” were experienced and acted upon by residents and organisations in each site in the context of the pandemic. Thus, our presentation and discussion of findings are structured along these dimensions.

3.1 Locations

Research question 5.1 – shared locations: How did spatial system conditions and spatialised practices mediate COVID-19 impacts and responses in the sub-national research sites?

Prior research demonstrates **correlations between COVID-19 indicators and place-based factors:** for instance, between incidence rates, hospitalisation rates, and/or death rates on the one hand and local socio-economic status and social demographics (Adhikari et al. 2020; Van Holm et al. 2020; Oluyumi et al. 2021; Zhang et al. 2021); population density (Van Holm et al. 2020; Lak et al. 2021); capacity to socially isolate (Carrión et al. 2020); neighbourhood resource distribution (Lak et al. 2021); and transportation infrastructure (Oluyumi et al. 2021; Zhang et al. 2021). On an individual level, Chen (2021) suggests that different spatialised social practices can impact both exposure to COVID-19 and vulnerability to the negative side effects of pandemic response measures, such as lockdown-related social isolation and loneliness.

Interviews with CSO representatives conducted during COVINFORM confirmed the importance of spatial factors during the pandemic. Many described the sites in which they worked as marked by **spatialised vulnerabilities**, such as poor infrastructure; above-average unemployment and/or precarious employment; dense and precarious housing conditions; houseless/homelessness; physical and psychological health disparities; digital divides; dependence upon social services; and lack of social integration and/or cohesion (COVINFORM D6.3, p. 69). The pandemic generally multiplied such vulnerabilities, thus worsening spatialised inequality in the target cities. This trend was aggravated by the restriction of in-person access to critical services: in some cases, access by telephone remained possible, whereas in other cases, telephone access also fell away, leaving online access as the only option. CSO interviewees reported new pressure to provide support services outside their traditional scopes of activity, including to individuals who did not need such services before the pandemic. For instance, CSO interviewees reported an increase in requests for assistance in accessing governmental services that had previously been accessible in-person, but that moved online in response to restrictions (ibid., p. 72). Many interviewees reported that it was critical to continue their street-level work with as few interruptions as possible. Several clarified that maintaining an on-site lifeline was crucial to prevent vulnerable individuals from falling through the gaps, as once that occurred, restoring contact might be difficult or impossible (ibid., p. 73).

Interviews with low-SES women conducted during COVINFORM further confirmed that individuals' immediate surroundings shaped their experiences of the pandemic. Moving outward from the interviewee in concentric circles, influential factors included:

- Characteristics of personal living spaces
- Characteristics of neighbourhoods, e.g., infrastructure and availability of services/resources
- Characteristics of cities, e.g., greenspace

A number of residents, especially those living in dense urban areas, mentioned the **limitations of their personal living spaces**. During periods of lockdown in particular, being stuck in small apartments and having one's scope of movement restricted led to feelings of confinement and claustrophobia. For interviewees with families, the close quarters sometimes exacerbated interpersonal tensions, especially since there were fewer opportunities for individual family members to withdraw and decompress. Conversely, the pandemic also stimulated some interviewees to new appreciation of positive features of their personal living spaces, such as terraces/balconies.

"I have the circumstance that I live in a house of 60 square meters, but luckily we have a small terrace, a balcony. Because it's been horrible to be there, between four walls, in so little space and not being able to go out to the street. Imagine that with an 11-year-old child, who has behaved well and has not complained much. But that was terrible." (Resident_Interview_6_ESP)

"Being at home all day was like I felt like I wanted to go out, at least to go out to the balcony to get some air." (Resident_Interview_12_ESP)

"So there's four of us in this house. It is a big house but I feel like at that that time, it wasn't enough for me to walk around and I felt claustrophobic. I felt a bit suffocating because we were all living in the same house and we're literally being stuck in the same house like maybe a year, a year and a half before COVID lockdown lift up. But yeah like we were literally at each other's throat." (Resident_Interview_1_E)

"The living environment during Corona, I said, was connected with difficulties all the time. And with that [points to the children] – yes, much more difficult. Well, with 50m² and three children. But the neighbours, thank God, I have good neighbors [...] the environment outside where I go, overall it weakened my psyche a lot, because it was very hard for me. Always with these children, three children. Then the language barrier, with their language [i.e., German]. I understand a lot but not so well." (Resident_Interview_3_AT)

Interviewees were quite cognizant of the fact that housing conditions and socioeconomic status are intertwined. Some of those interviewees that experienced feelings of confinement either fantasised about living in more accommodating spaces, or stated that the pandemic had made them reconsider their housing situations and needs (though in many cases, economic barriers might complicate actually finding new housing).

"If I had a villa, there would have been no problems (laughs). But in such a small apartment. It wasn't possible to go to the park. I could just go to the shop to pick up bread. And then go directly home. Even doing shopping... everyone was so scared to go outside. As if it was a battlefield." (Resident_Interview_6_BLG)

"What I missed here was one of those terraces that were on TV, where people came out. If I had had a terrace or one of those villas with a garden..." (Resident_Interview_1_ESP)

“And we don't get an apartment easily either, so [housing services] doesn't give us an apartment. We are forced to find an apartment privately, and well, if you look for it yourself, it's expensive, expensive. So for now we have to stay in this apartment, in a 51m² apartment, we are five people. Let's see what will happen in the future years.” (Resident_Interview_3_AT)

A mitigation strategy adopted by some interviewees – albeit a minority within the sample – was the enthusiastic pursuit of **new hobbies that were possible in confined spaces**, such as crafting or cooking and baking. Such hobbies gave interviewees a sense of solace and helped them to reconnect in meaningful ways with their living spaces and social circles, and to experience them as intimate rather than merely claustrophobic.

“The last two years. We've been baking biscuits. We started in the middle of November and finished almost at the end of December, like that. It was crazy. Yeah, we did a lot of that, baking, and baking, and baking again” (Resident_Interview_9_AT)

Moving outward from the personal living space to the neighbourhood, a number of respondents mentioned **physical and digital infrastructure and resource deficits**. Some indicated that their neighbourhoods lacked sufficient medical facilities and services, e.g., clinics, pharmacies, etc. One interviewee living in a long-term care facility in an underserved neighbourhood furthermore mentioned a decrease in the frequency of visits by medical specialists.

“But for example the doctor doesn't come anymore and it's a pity that we don't have one. Of course, we don't stay because if you need the doctor, well it's not going to be the pharmacist or the woman from the east who comes to take care of us and to look at us. There has to be a doctor who comes and there is nobody here.” (Resident_Interview_5_ESP)

A number of interviewees found local digital infrastructures lacking. Under normal conditions, libraries provide a chance for those without home connections to access the internet; however, lockdowns and other social distancing regulations blocked this access route. Several interviewees explicitly suggested expanding online access as a comparatively easy step that authorities could take to improve wellbeing during the next public health crisis.

“More gigabytes, more Wi-Fi, more frequency. So that everyone, especially people in poverty, can receive it for free. You have that in the library, sometimes you see children waiting outside for it. But then you have to be on the street.” (Resident_Interview_6_BLG)

Likewise, for interviewees with children, access to proper schooling emerged as a challenge. During lockdown, many schools switched to a distance learning model – however, not all parents, nor schools, were equipped with adequate technical resources. Digital divides (mentioned above) exacerbated this problem in some of the interviewees' neighbourhoods. Some interviewees were furthermore highly critical of whether home schooling models were effective at all. Working mothers within the sample furthermore sometimes had difficulty adapting to children being at home; some made it clear that gendered expectations on divisions of labour meant that their workloads increased significantly.

“When the children were locked in the house, they didn't learn anything, they didn't know anything, they were kept in the house.” (Resident_Interview_10_RO)

“They missed a lot and with this home schooling, home schooling also not everything worked out as we wished. Because some, the kids learn differently with teacher than mom. I had to

*clean, cook, explain homework before they also have this conference”
(Resident_Interview_7_DE)*

Overall, a trend appeared toward reduced access to numerous health and social infrastructure and resources for the low-SES women interviewed. In many sites, this trend collided with an equally challenging trend of **poor access to public transport**: in some neighbourhoods, transportation infrastructure was already poor, while others suffered from a reduction in capacity. This prevented interviewees from accessing resources in other areas of their cities (interviewees in Italy [Rome] and Spain [Madrid] appeared particularly dissatisfied with public transportation infrastructure in their neighbourhoods).

“Public transport was terrible. They were full and they would even leave you and walk away. So many people were left on the streets. Then at the end they increased a little bit but not for the places a little bit isolated, still nothing.” (Resident_Interview_1_IT)

Another factor discussed by a number of interviewees was **friction with local authorities**, especially police. Many described a heightened police presence on the streets, which brought with it general feelings of tension and apprehension. Some stated that they took special care to adhere to regulations, or avoided certain behaviours or places, due to fear of being arrested or fined. Others mentioned having received fines themselves, or seen others being arrested or fined. On the contrary, other respondents expressed a wish for more police presence. Finally, a handful of interviewees (all in Romania) testify to having witnessed or having been subject to **police brutality. This is a critical finding that demands further investigation**, in concert with systematic research on local law enforcement policies and administrative data (e.g., on police and ombudsman reports, or comparable sources).

“I was in the city to get something and then the demonstration started and then I also looked. And I say honestly. It was really intense. The police were also, shall I say, more aggressive. I didn't go to that. In the end, I was still counting on it....there was also the whole police thing, where police officers are somehow bad and quickly resort to violence. That scared me a bit, because here in Mannheim the police were really aggressive and shouted around. I also noticed that they were also very violent.” (Resident_Interview_12_DE)

*“I think there should have been more control by the police or so why people did not respect the distancing, the queues for the pharmacy or supermarkets were all on top of each other, I thought very badly, the masks do not protect 100% and people did not respect anything.”
(Resident_Interview_6_PT)*

*“Well, if I went to the shops, I still stayed at a distance, with a mask on my mouth because the police caught us many times, they also fined me [...] They changed from 7 in the morning to 7 in the evening and patrolled the whole street, police and masked armed forces”
(Resident_Interview_8_RO)*

“It was this neighbourhood, you couldn't really go outside, there was the police, those that they caught outside they would beat them [...] They caught them on the street and beat them. Three men came to pick me up, it was very bad with the police. Everyone was crying, everyone didn't know what to do. It was very bad.” (Resident_Interview_9_RO)

“I went out to the gate a little, the police commander saw me from his car, I took the laundry, the children went out to the gate, I took the laundry from the clothesline and went out after them to pull them in because they were not allowed on the road, and then they came and they

beat me in the yard [...] And my boy said 'don't beat my mother anymore, because she is sick'. And he gave in after that. I fell down, and then he started hitting my boy. But as I was down, people shouted not to hit my child. I was saying not to kill my child." (Resident_Interview_7_RO)

In addition to discussing spatial limitations that exacerbated their vulnerabilities, interviewees mentioned **spatial resources that augmented their wellbeing**. Among the most frequently mentioned such resources were family and friends living nearby. A number of interviewees furthermore stated that the pandemic brought them closer to their neighbours: the sense of undergoing a common challenge, as well as opportunities to provide mutual aid and support, drove an increase in feelings of **neighbourhood cohesion** and identity.

"What I felt is that with all those people living in the neighborhood is that we felt closer, like a family. We would learn that a neighbor would get infected and would care about them to see if he/she was alright. We felt as if we were going through this situation altogether." (Resident_Interview_6_GR)

"[I felt and appreciated] the closeness of the neighbors and their willingness to help each other" (Resident_Interview_6_ESP)

For some interviewees, **access to nature** was another critical pathway for psychological decompression and physical exercise. During periods of hard lockdown, even access to fresh air via a balcony could feel like a significant relief from claustrophobia. When regulations allowed it, interviewees visited parks and, for those with children, playgrounds. Some reported a new sense of appreciation for these simple pleasures.

"Well, it would have been much easier if you had a balcony, but if you...well, I think people would get stupid if they had to squat in the apartment all the time. So, that you're already allowed to, I don't know, 15 minutes a day at least maybe go out for a walk, get some air, go for a walk, whatever. (Resident_Interview_12_DE)

"What really helped was that in my local community there are a lot of green spaces and we could walk in a green environment, despite many businesses being closed during the pandemic." (Resident_Interview_11_GR)

"The children are different when they go to the park, they feel different." (Resident_Interview_10_RO)

3.2 Social ties

Research question 5.2 – shared social relations: How did social networks mediate COVID-19 impacts in the sub-national research sites?

Social networks played an important role in the evolution of both the pandemic and the accompanying information landscape (including the so-called "infodemic" of mis- and disinformation). With regard to the pandemic itself, social contact was, of course, a vector for transmission; aggregated Facebook data suggests that highly interconnected **social network structures can predict the spread of COVID-19** (Kuchler et al. 2020). This fact underpins the strategy of non-pharmaceutical intervention pursued in most countries, which centred on regulating in-person social contact as well as incentivising hygiene and other health-protective measures.

However, as quickly became evident, in-person social contact and **social networks are irreplaceable in people's lives**. Prior studies have shown that robust social networks can increase resilience in the physical/health, social, economic, and informational domains; on the contrary, smaller or disrupted social networks can aggravate mental and physical health problems – especially among vulnerable populations, such as ethnic minorities (Gauthier et al. 2021). CSO representatives interviewed in COVINFORM indicated that within their vulnerable target groups, social networks played a critical role in shoring up psychological wellbeing and disseminating both material support and information. This appears particularly to have been the case within populations with limited access to, or trust in, governmental social welfare systems. For these populations, social contact restrictions were doubly harmful: they not only closed off the face-to-face channels by which institutional support was most frequently accessed, but also but also disrupted place-based informal support networks that served equally or even more important roles (COVINFORM D6.3, p. 71).

The COVINFORM resident interviews confirm that the pandemic disrupted their social networks and transformed their patterns of interaction. The most overwhelmingly common impact reported by interviewees was **reduced social contact** and a consequent, palpable sense of isolation. For many interviewees, diverse types of social interaction – ranging from spontaneous and casual meetups to parties and events – were an important part of life. Lockdowns, and to a lesser extent other non-pharmaceutical interventions, severely constricted the range of types of socialization available to interviewees. This reduced their quality of life. Even in 2022, when most regulations had been phased out, some interviewees described a lingering yearning for the return of a sometimes ill-defined “normality”, i.e., (real or imagined) pre-pandemic conditions.

“I like partying, meetings with friends, concerts, wind, beach, being with people [...] then when the restrictions began to ease was the recovery” (Resident_Interview_10_PT)

“We live with the hope that we will return to our normality in the future. Most measures ceased but we haven't returned to normality.” (Resident_Interview_9_GR)

For interviewees whose families and friendship groups spanned international borders, travel restrictions also had a disruptive impact on social networks, and accordingly, personal wellbeing. Migrant and migration-background interviewees in particular often reported emotional stress due to prolonged separation from family members during difficult times. This was especially the case when family members lived in countries with deficient public health systems, which suffered poor outcomes during the pandemic.

“I remember a lot, yes. Very terrible. And at a certain time it wasn't so bad in Sweden, but in my home country Iran it was actually very terrible.” (Resident_Interview_6_SE)

“So, we had many relatives who died because of Corona. We weren't allowed to go to the funeral. We didn't get.” (Resident_Interview_3_SE)

The COVINFORM interviewees utilized a number of **strategies to maintain their social networks** during periods of the pandemic when social distancing was mandatory. A majority – especially those who were older – used the telephone as their primary channel. Drivers were convenience, familiarity, and a feeling of warmth conveyed by the voice. Most, however, also used messenger platforms for quick, asynchronous communication. Most also sometimes used video calling, both for conversations with individual family members or friends and for group calls. Some interviewees liked the ability to see their conversation partners, whereas others cited technical challenges or the impersonal nature of

video calling as deterrents. Notably, very few interviewees mentioned using video calling platforms for work – this is likely because the majority of interviewees did not work in sectors in which this was a possibility (e.g., more ‘frontline’ than administrative work).

“We usually talk to each other quite a lot on the phone.” (Resident_Interview_1_SE)

“I mean, I talk to them on the phone, but that's all, I don't use social networks or WhatsApp or anything like that.” (Resident_Interview_11_PT)

“My [smart]phone. Whatsapp mostly, writing, mostly writing.” (Resident_Interview_3_DE)

“Especially [it was a relief] that we can talk well on the phone – well, not by phone, but by videoconference, where you see the faces and you are on video, because there is nothing like that.” (Resident_Interview_5_ESP)

“Yes, I always video call with my brothers in Peru.” (Resident_Interview_2_IT)

Social networks also played a central role in the **informational dimension of the pandemic**. Prior case studies in a range of sites showed that peer-to-peer contacts, particularly on social media, were an important vector for pandemic communication – sometimes including the spread of mis- and disinformation (Cuello-Garcia, Pérez-Gaxiola, & van Amelsvoort 2021). The COVINFORM resident interviews echoed this finding: clear patterns emerged in terms of preferred communication channels and trusted information sources. Here, a distinction can be made between:

- **Primary crisis and risk communication**, i.e., information received from official sources or news organisations; and
- **Secondary crisis and risk communication**, i.e., information received from ‘informal’ sources, such as face-to-face communication or social media.

When asked about their COVID-19 information-seeking behaviour, most interviewees made it clear that they had diverse information repertoires – which is to say, they received information from a broad spectrum of primary and secondary communicators. However, **secondary crisis communication was often top-of-mind**. Interviewees explicitly or implicitly offered numerous reasons for preferring secondary communication: e.g., access to quick updates and real-time information, the perceived credibility of information provided by people they knew vs. the perceived disconnect between information provided by official sources and conditions ‘on the street’, and the ability to comment and share personal experiences and sympathy.

“The information [...] above all from friends, from people you know and people you know who know about the subject. With all these things that I've told you about the concealment of facts and things that didn't add up for me every time, I trusted less what was said on TV, more than anything else because you could also see something completely different on the street. Therefore, I paid more attention to the people we understood and who were friends.” (Resident_Interview_3_ESP)

“Yes, we exchanged information on social media sites and gave each other comfort.” (Resident_Interview_11_DE)

Conversely, many interviewees also expressed uncertainty about the credibility and quality of information accessible via social media. Some reported being targeted with virulent disinformation, which was highly upsetting and threw their trust into question.

“Yes, I came across a lot of misinformation on social media. There were many false claims and conspiracy theories circulating about the virus, the vaccine, and the measures being taken. It was difficult to separate fact from fiction, so I tried to rely on trusted news sources and official guidelines to stay informed. It was important to be cautious and not spread or believe in information that was not verified.” (Resident_Interview_1_W)

“Of course, there are some sites that I cannot trust. I’ve witnessed that some articles have a specific title and the content differed from the title. I’ve also seen that some sites deliberately intend to agitate readers or create uneasiness for no particular reason.” (Resident_Interview_1_GR)

“One time someone had sent a message or something. It was a WhatsApp sent around to people. But it was a deliberate lie. They said in Spain, the reason that corona exists is to kill the parents on purpose, and take away the children from the parents. I panicked then, I thought that was real. They said that they kill foreign people on purpose, to take their children from them.” (Resident_Interview_3_BLG)

These same respondents often expressed a preference for governmental information sources or traditional news organisations, which offered the benefits of authority, clarity, and consistency. Trust in these sources appeared to falter when these benefits came into question: for instance, when reports appeared to contradict or shift from day to day.

“I trust only the ORF” (Resident_Interview_2_AT)

“Yes, newspapers. Or TV. Yes. All of these. Every day.” (Resident_Interview_8_SE)

“We used to watch TV and see what they were saying there, how to do it. And we were avoiding infection.” (Resident_Interview_1_RO)

“I had no other, what they said on TV, it's true that I saw the news on different channels and well, you have no other choice but to trust, you have no other choice because you don't have anything else. But it is true that at the beginning everything was very contradictory. One day they said one thing and another day they said something else. One day they said that it was not necessary to wear masks, another day they said that it was very important to wear masks.” (Resident_Interview_2_ESP)

While the aim of the COVINFORM research was not to produce quantifiable representative data on information repertoires, it is credible to hypothesise that respondents fall on a quasi-normal distribution (“bell curve”) between two extremes: those who mostly consulted and trusted primary risk communication sources, and those who mostly consulted and trusted secondary risk communication sources. The majority appear to sit between these extremes, consulting both types of sources and making assessments about credibility on a case-by-case basis. Based on the qualitative findings, it can be reasonably hypothesised that heavy social media use and/or a preference for secondary crisis communication via social media over primary crisis communication correlates with susceptibility to mis- and disinformation and belief in conspiracy theories. For more on conspiracy theories, see the below section on shared attitudes and practices.

Finally, the resident interviews made it clear that a substantial number of low-SES women experienced at least some **difficulty obtaining clear, reliable information**. Some interviewees mentioned ‘hard’ technical barriers, such as lack of reliable internet access, whereas others appeared hampered by a

digital skill divide: e.g., not knowing how to navigate to credible sources or use search engines in a way that enables the discovery of credible sources.

“I mean, everything now goes online and yet here we don't even have internet, just the wifi that there is or the phone coverage, which is not everywhere. They put up an antenna that no longer works.” (Resident_Interview_5_ESP)

“I really only have very big questions about two things, that is about vaccines and about the lack of information and clarification on the part of nurses and doctors. Because no one explained anything to me – I always trusted science, but suddenly I'm questioning everything” (Resident_Interview_11_PT)

3.3 Joint action

Research question 5.3 – shared activities: What roles have CSOs, grassroots initiatives, and residents played in the provision of health and social services in the sub-national research sites?

The pandemic offered a real-time ‘stress test’ for **different approaches to multi-level governance**: for example, centralised vs. decentralised and injunction-based vs. incentive-based (Kuhlmann et al. 2021); “proactive” vs. “reactive” (Anttiroiko 2021), etc. This also applies specifically to different approaches to multi-level risk communication (Hanson et al. 2021).

In WP4 of the COVINFORM project, which focused on governmental responses, it was determined that most target states developed specialised COVID-19 response task forces, under the supervision of the Ministries of Health, which closely cooperated with national, regional and local governments (COVINFORM D4.8, p. 40). Some defined response measures primarily on a national level (Greece, Italy, Portugal), while others set general guidelines on a national level and devolved responsibility for specific measures to sub-national administrative units (Austria, Belgium, Germany, Spain, Sweden, UK) (ibid.). Representatives of governmental institutions interviewed within the WP identified preparedness – including **prepared frameworks for cooperation between levels and with civil society** – as a key topic. Good practices were the utilization of pre-existing pandemic plans and crisis response structures, as well as the socio-political willingness to conduct pre-emptive actions in order to compensate for systemic weaknesses. Respondents across countries also concurred on critical weaknesses: these included unclear administrative boundaries, blurry areas of responsibility, and poor communication between different administrative units, or between administrations and civil society, frustrated response measures.

The CSO representative interviews conducted in WP6 offer a civil society perspective on this nexus of interaction. The CSOs represented within the sample included organisations providing various types of material support (e.g., housing, food, etc.); physical and psychological health services; women’s services; children’s, youth, and family services; services oriented toward refugees and other migrants; services oriented toward ethnic and linguistic minority populations; etc. Interviewees indicated that **CSOs in the target sites cooperated extensively with other actors** – other CSOs, authorities, and residents, as well as sometimes other organisations such as IGOs and businesses – to fill the gaps in the social welfare and healthcare systems. They did so by: 1) assisting people in overcoming access barriers to governmental services; and 2) providing additional services, often including on-site or mobile/door-to-door healthcare, including vaccinations; counselling and socio-psychological support; legal support; accommodations; distribution of basic necessities; and multilingual, culturally targeted health and risk communication (COVINFORM D6.3, p. 74-75).

CSO interviewees also indicated that **residents themselves often played an active role** in the response. In all target sites, grassroots initiatives were established by residents, often in collaboration with local governments or CSOs (ibid., p. 77-78). Such cooperation was perceived as helpful both at the stage of planning response measures (to ensure target group relevance) and at the stage of implementing them (to ensure access and impact). Multiple interviewees mentioned that cooperative efforts taken during the pandemic have considerably strengthened the relationships between organizations and with residents, which is only beneficial for the future. With merged forces, a variety of thematic areas can be covered and is certainly helpful to address different vulnerable groups. Desk research in the target site confirmed the role of numerous participatory practices in local responses, ranging from simple online platforms on which day-to-day assistance could be offered and requested, to complex and specialised initiatives to co-produce medical equipment, code crisis response apps, etc. Numerous examples are provided in COVINFORM D6.5.

The resident interview findings shed additional light on both successes and failures in multi-level pandemic governance; the relative perceived importance of different actors such as GOs and CSOs; and residents' own participation in pandemic response measures. The COVID-19 pandemic hit respondents unprepared, disrupting their lives, daily routines, and safety nets. The majority felt overwhelmed, helpless, and in urgent need of support. The extent to which response measures taken by different actors fulfilled this need varied greatly among interviewees. For many, the institutions formally responsible for managing the crisis – e.g., public health and social welfare systems – were not the first actors spontaneously mentioned when the topic of support was raised. Indeed, for many, **family and friends were top-of-mind as sources of aid**: which is to say, mutual aid mediated by ties of blood and friendship proved to be invaluable. Family and friends not only provided emotional support, but also often played an active role in providing material resources – including in cases where governmental or civil society efforts fell short.

*“I think we all supported each other, friends and family, even though at a distance, the fact that we kept in touch over the phone and so was an important psychological help.”
(Resident_Interview_9_PT)*

“I also asked to the social worker for help, but she could not help me because there were so many of us asking for help and I was at least working. They helped the people who weren't working first. They told me the same at Caritas.”

“Especially a dear friend called Roberta, she also lent me money to pay the bills, now I have a debt of 4000 euro with her.” (Resident_Interview_12_IT)

Surprisingly, **state mechanisms were seldom mentioned** by respondents who had not received direct financial benefits or relief packages. This may be because many governmental support schemes did not target natural persons, but rather entities such as businesses, CSOs, the creative and cultural sectors and industries, etc. The indirect or 'knock-on' benefits of such broader support schemes were not widely acknowledged – though it is unclear whether this is due to lack of awareness or lack of perceived personal relevance.

“I have not received any help from the government. It's all been on a private level [...] I am happy with the people I know, not with the government. The government, do you think that man is going to know how we are in every house? Well, nothing, it is impossible. They are doing their own thing, to generate the rules and we obey. And the government doesn't care if I pay for the electricity or not. I haven't received anything from the social services. I do know that

there have been elderly people who have had their groceries brought to them, and so on.” (Resident_Interview_6_ESP)

“I think there were people who have become very ill because they worked on green receipts and have been left with no money in the lockdowns, I think the state doesn't look after the poor.” (Resident_Interview_6_PT)

By contrast, a number of interviewees stated that **CSOs provided diverse kinds of support** at crucial junctures. One type of CSO activity mentioned frequently by the low-SES target population was the provision of food, clothing, and other basic necessities. Here, on-site access was key: interviewees benefited from the certainty of knowing what physical site to visit if they needed something as fundamental as food or a blanket. A secondary benefit here was social contact (however brief) with the staff or volunteers staffing the site.

“Caritas also gave us a lot of [material] help.” (Resident_Interview_8_ESP)

“At the time, the first symptoms, yes, we bought them [masks and sanitiser], but afterwards, the Red Cross gave me a carton of about 50 masks, and one of the girls who lived there, they also gave her some hydrogel” (Resident_Interview_8_ESP)

A number of interviewees mentioned benefitting from (online) socio-psychological services, via a range of providers: CSOs, professional organisations and initiatives, and even private individuals within their extended social networks.

“I did not receive different or extraordinary support, but I kept psychotherapy appointments often, via online” (Resident_Interview_2_PT)

“I receive psychological support from a psychological coach from Texas, via social media. She's a professional psychologist but due to being acquainted with a friend of mine, she has also been helping me for free.” (Resident_Interview_3_GR)

Religious organisations – both large foundations such as Caritas and local churches, synagogues, and mosques – were especially present in the multi-stakeholder pandemic response. They not only collected and distributed basic necessities, but also provided contact points for spiritual and social support, either on-site or via home visits.

“But after the pandemic we went to the church. (...) they wrote to us and gave us these packages once a month.” (Resident_Interview_2_IT)

“The people of the church always help me with food and just because as I am diabetic I cannot eat much, I have to be careful with food and for me it is not easy to go shopping, here at home I also had help in shopping food and pharmacy and so, the church also helps me with clothes.” (Resident_Interview_4_PT)

“A little sister in the church, she gave me, in the Christian church we say, a blessing.” (Resident_Interview_13_ESP)

“I have friends from the church who come to visit me” (Resident_Interview_4_PT)

Notably, CSO representatives interviewed in many target sites confirmed that cooperation between secular and religious institutions was important. In multiple countries (e.g. Germany, Greece, Italy, Sweden, UK), religious communities were heavily engaged in solidarity actions in partnership with the interviewees or other CSOs, providing food or essential goods to vulnerable people within their

communities. Religious leaders often collaborated with local authorities as well as secular CSOs to help implement COVID-19 measures, share reliable information, or act as translators and mediators within communities with whom they enjoyed trust (COVINFORM D6.3, p. 78).

In addition to support from secular and religious CSOs and their volunteer networks, a number of low-SES women interviewed in the target sites mentioned receiving **support from neighbours**. In some cases such support was organised via neighbourhood associations or platforms (e.g., <https://nebenan.de/>), while in other cases it arose through simple informal contact with individual neighbours.

*“There was a neighbourhood association that came and brought packages three times.”
(Resident_Interview_1_IT)*

“I have contact with my neighbour as well, I did her shopping and then she also helped me when I had to stay and quarantine.” (Resident_Interview_5_BLG)

Some neighbours indicated that they **provided assistance to neighbours** in turn (e.g., sharing material resources or assisting with errands for those in isolation or quarantine). These proactive interviewees viewed themselves in a number of ways: as simply acting in a humane way, as following a (religious or secular) ethical code, or as connectors within the community, helping to bridge needs with resources that can fill them (for more on this, see Edwards, 2022). However, none of the residents interviewed explicitly indicated that they were involved in organising or helping to organise more formal mutual aid initiatives (e.g., of the type explored in COVINFORM D6.5).

*“At the time when everything came up, my focus and will was to be of service and help.”
(Resident_Interview_12_PT)*

*“I’ve given psychological support through my telephone to my friends.”
(Resident_Interview_10_GR)*

“There is an old woman who is also an addict, that’s interesting. In the time of Corona, she came and said ‘I have a fever’, because she is addicted, and when she knocks on our door and wants something, I never refuse [...] the poor thing came again, she had a fever and it was Corona’s peak, she cried and said ‘I have no credit’. God is my witness, I gave my phone. I gave my phone, and she said ‘call 144’. I called them and said, I don’t speak German very well, you speak. My sister then said, ‘what if she had Corona’, and was angry. I put on gloves, as God is my witness, switched off the phone and disinfected it [laughs] [...] At Corona’s peak I didn’t refuse her. God said one must not turn away the needy.” (Resident_Interview_11_AT)

Finally, while most interviewees indicated that they had received various types of support from a range of sources, it was evident that gaps in the response remain. A substantial number of interviewees reported receiving **limited or no assistance** during phases of the pandemic. Specifically, respondents in multiple sites mentioned difficulty accessing food and other basic necessities, COVID-related and general health services, and/or socio-psychological support. The latter deficit appears to have been particularly severe: even among interviewees who did not specifically mention trying and failing to find psychological support, a great many reported suffering from loneliness or other psychological impacts and not knowing where to turn. Only a minority of interviewees took a critical stance, linking these negative experiences to deficits in governmental and/or CSO response measures – it is conceivable that this is because the target population of low-SES women are habituated to being overlooked

“We had no food, no detergent to wash with, no food to cook.” (Resident_Interview_1_RO)

“First in the hospital in quarantine, so to speak, because I had to lie in bed, and then you come home, you're finally happy, but you're also locked up again. No food, nothing at home, no.” (Resident_Interview_8_AT)

“We didn't get help. Not the emergency room, not the health centre - they didn't treat us. Especially when winter came [...] my children, they have ear infections, they have ear problems. When they get a cold, they get an ear and throat infection, and they have to have antibiotics. And when you say they have symptoms - exactly like Corona symptoms - they say 'no, but you can't come'.” (Resident_Interview_3_SE)

“For me, I will say more emotional support like therapy or something because I know a lot of people have – pandemic has really affected a lot of people's mental health in terms of for them not to see people and for them not to live the lifestyle they normally have” (Resident_Interview_1_E)

3.4 Shared attitudes and practices

Research question 5.4 – shared attitudes and practices: How did shared attitudes, beliefs, and practices – including shared trust – mediate COVID-19 impacts in the sub-national research sites?

Prior studies have demonstrated that shared attitudes, beliefs, and practices have mediated the impacts of the pandemic and response measures in a range of complex ways. **Shared pro-social attitudes and behaviours** (i.e., “civic capital”) have been found to correlate with lower COVID-19 transmission rates (Durante et al. 2020). The cultural tendency to avoid uncertainty and collective experiences of past pandemics may improve acceptance of social distancing (Huynh 2020; Lee et al. 2021), while shared “moral principles of fairness and care” often correlate with higher levels of trust in science (Pagliaro et al. 2021). Similarly, **high levels of interpersonal trust** may reduce “pandemic fatigue” and increase willingness to engage in burdensome protective behaviours over an extended period (Petherick et al. 2021). Just as high levels of social cohesion and trust can improve compliance with pandemic response measures, low levels of social cohesion and trust can prove a severe barrier. As COVID-19-related media became more politicised throughout the crisis, shared political attitudes played an increasingly important role in trust formation. Political attitudes have been found to predict attitudes toward COVID-19 risk, response policies, and information (including susceptibility to mis- and disinformation) (Weil and Wolfe 2021). Accordingly, taking account of shared attitudes and behaviours is a critical step in developing sound risk communication strategies, especially insofar as such shared attitudes and behaviours intersect with health and/or socioeconomic vulnerabilities (Airhihenbuwa 2020; Anson et al. 2021).

CSO representatives interviewed in the ten COVINFORM target sites universally stressed the **importance of trust**. Interviewees from a variety of countries (e.g., Spain, Greece, Portugal, and Wales) also indicated the **significance of social cohesion** (COVINFORM D6.3, p. 75). One positive impact of the pandemic noted by some interviewees was an increased sense of social cohesion and “community”, as manifest in widespread willingness to donate, volunteer, and otherwise participate actively in the crisis response. Interviewees were divided on the question of whether this would persist after the crisis: some expressed hope for a long-term awakening of community solidarity and increased societal awareness of the needs of vulnerable groups, while others predicted that momentum would decrease as conditions returned to ‘normal’. Some pessimistic voices went further, predicting that the pandemic could have a long-term chilling effect on social relationships (ibid., pp. 75-76).

As noted in the above sections on “location” and “joint action”, a number of low-SES women interviewed in the ten COVINFORM sites also mentioned an increased sense of neighbourhood cohesion and an uptick in practices of mutual aid as rare positive impacts of the pandemic. However, the interviews also revealed **fragmentation along lines of differing beliefs and practices**.

“It has also been an issue that sometimes people have not agreed, because those who were very afraid distrusted those who were a little less afraid and were less careful. So, well, it has been a very strange situation, very strange.” (Resident_Interview_6_ESP)

“Many have separated, many partners have separated, precisely because of Corona, because there was no unanimity and many friends have also fallen out, because one has said that vaccination is better and the other has said, no, I will not be vaccinated as long as I do not know what is in the vaccine. Simply divided opinions. I have to say, of course, we also had arguments about Corona, because my husband sees these rules a bit more seriously and I saw them a bit more loosely, but in the end we are still together [laughs].” (Resident_Interview_10_DE)

“Because we have friends who are anti-vaccination, I had the worry at a certain point that this argument or outcast feeling will escalate to something that will lose control.” (Resident_Interview_1_BLG)

The key fault line here was trust in the authority of ‘mainstream’ institutions: governments, science, and the press, as well as established CSOs. Around half of those interviewed adhered to a more or less **‘mainstream’ approach**: fundamental (if sometimes critical) acceptance of the emergent scientific consensus on COVID-19, the legitimacy of COVID-19 response measures, the credibility of official risk and crisis communications, the efficacy and safety of vaccines, etc.

“I think this measure was a good measure. For example, social distancing, vaccination, the mask.” (Resident_Interview_15_ESP)

“I still wear a mask when I go shopping.” (Resident_Interview_1_DE)

Conversely, around half leaned toward a **‘rejectionist’ approach**: rejection of the reality of COVID-19 or openness to conspiracy theories about its origin and nature; rejection of the legitimacy of response measures; a preference for non-official information sources, including sources linked to mis- or disinformation; etc. The most frequent targets of scepticism were vaccination, lockdowns, and mask-wearing, as well as the overall credibility of authorities.

“And on the internet, the social media, I always [...] so, I researched some doctors, [who said] so you shouldn't vaccinate and you shouldn't do that.” (Resident_Interview_10_AT)

“So, for example, when it came on the news how many people died. So, I think we would have to be underpopulated to believe that. I still don't believe it today [...] That they all died from Corona. That's impossible! [...] Yeah. So, to me, Corona is a normal flu infection.” (Resident_Interview_1_DE)

“And Corona, I don't know now who invented that [...] Some say it's man-made and some say no, [it came from] the animals” (Resident_Interview_3_AT)

It is noteworthy that in some cases, the acceptance of ‘mainstream’ behaviours did not necessarily imply full confidence in authorities, but rather, respect for others, a desire to take the path of least resistance, and a desire to avoid being socially disruptive (social desirability). Indeed, rather than falling

into two dichotomous camps, most respondents can better be described as falling on a continuum between the ‘mainstream’ and ‘rejectionist’ extremes.

“Basically, I was trying to follow the requests of the authorities. I didn’t feel like going against it and I didn’t see a reason. And not out of respect for the authorities but mutual respect for the people that surround me and I’m working with other people around me. If I go on the train or public transport there are other people around me. Or any public space. I think it is just basic mutual respect. At a certain moment, yeah, the trust a little bit was shaken, but it was not a good enough reason to say I am anti-mask or anything.” (Resident_Interview_1_BLG)

Despite the fact that rejectionist views were not rare, only a small minority of interviewees admitted to **non-compliance with regulations** or non-vaccination. Many interviewees who harboured scepticism as to the legitimacy or efficacy of government measures complied with them anyway, for the above reasons. Among those who violated regulations, reasons given ranged from personal necessity (e.g., health conditions) to feelings of rebellion to simply not caring. Reasons given for non-vaccination were often more complex, entailing low confidence in the vaccine development process and the safety of the available vaccines, fear over potentially complicating prior conditions, critical attitudes toward the pharmaceutical industry, etc. These factors were all often aggravated by a lack of accurate information, either due to wilful avoidance or simple uncertainty as to what information sources to trust.

“I met with [friends] twice and received a fine, because I didn't have a mask” (Resident_Interview_19_RO)

“I have a protein allergy. And there is protein everywhere in these vaccines. That's the first thing. And then I just think, if you get vaccinated, you can't build up an immune system.” (Resident_Interview_1_DE)

“They said vaccinate, and a lot of people got vaccinated and still died when they got Corona. And that is exactly why I said, why should I vaccinate when I have seen those who vaccinated, got Corona, and died?”. (Resident_Interview_3_AT)

“I'd rather die than suffer the consequences of the vaccination for the rest of my life [...] I watched a documentary last week, a German one, where many people also suffered damage from the vaccination. It was all so uncertain [...] I think, had they done a bit more research and then only brought out the vaccination, I don't know [...] also, my ex-in-laws, they had boosted three times and they still had violent Corona, very long, months.” (Resident_Interview_11_DE)

“I did not care for any news, I do not watch any television practically, and I could no longer hear more talk about COVID – I never wanted to, and never worried about any of this. I think it was all a joke. I'm not vaccinated nor will I be, this is all a rampant fuss [...] I think the information is all false, I do not believe in vaccines and their effectiveness” (Resident_Interview_5_PT)

Notably, there were also interviewees within the sample who openly criticised ‘rejectionist’ attitudes, either in a tone of concern or bemusement.

“A compatriot, she was also a bit older, I said to her, why didn't you get vaccinated? [...] Then she said, no, I heard from the others, those who get vaccinated stay alive for two years [laughs] – and after two years, they die [laughs].” (Resident_Interview_11_AT)

“I was careful with one of the neighbours. She's around 70, middle of 70s. She didn't have vaccinations, she doesn't believe in COVID, and she even said ‘if someone has the vaccine, don't go close to them, because they're just giving you a virus, something that is unsafe, because they say there's something in the air; they're just throwing this kind of air from the airplanes’, blah blah blah.” (Resident_Interview_1_W)

In addition to lack of trust and frustration, rejectionist beliefs and behaviours were undoubtedly rooted in the **overwhelmingly negative emotional impacts** of the pandemic. The predominant emotions experienced by a significant number of the low-SES women interviewed were fear for oneself and one's loved ones, distress due to separation from family and friends, loneliness due to disrupted social networks, feelings of melancholy due to disruptions to daily life and routines, and concern about the immediate impact of the pandemic on the economy and society (notably, the resident interviewees were less likely than the CSO interviewees to spontaneously mention the possibility of longer-term structural impacts).

“We were terrified, we would speak to each other, we heard other people coughing and were afraid of being infected too even if other people did not necessarily have COVID-19.” (Resident_Interview_6_GR)

“Then I think we went back into the second lockdown and things, I feel like, started to hit hard a little bit. You begin to feel isolated from the world” (Resident_Interview_2_E)

“I don't know, it was like you had an anguish in your stomach that didn't let you live. Then, since you weren't tired either, you didn't rest at night and it was a whole circle and more tiredness and more stress” (Resident_Interview_6_ESP)

Another phenomenon that arose in the resident interviews relevant to the topic of shared attitudes and practices was belief in the divine. A moderate number of low-SES women stated that religious beliefs and practices helped them make sense of the pandemic and find comfort during difficult periods. Some testified to the power of prayer, and a smaller number openly asked whether the pandemic might be a test or a sign from a higher power. This latter attitude could occasionally intersect with depression to yield quasi-apocalyptic expressions. Conversely, there were also interviewees who expressed alarm or bemusement at such expressions.

“I prayed for god and asked for help and that helped me overcome my depression. Religion works.” (Resident_Interview_6_BLG)

“We thank God that we are healthy and no one died.” (Resident_Interview_3_RO)

Sometimes I said, dear God, end the world at last. Let it all pass, so it can end. Why do you want to continue this?” (Resident_Interview_3_AT)

“I couldn't go [to church ...] Well, [I felt] sadness, because at least I liked to go to church there, because there we sang, we praised God, or at the time of sharing, we went out to worship, we shared, we talked, or we went somewhere with the sisters, they invited us to eat and everything, so, that affected us, especially me.” (Resident_Interview_13_ESP)

“People make reference to Islam now. ‘God makes everybody wear a niqab now, blah blah’. [They criticise] some people when they don't follow their religion, and say ‘they found their penalties’. Oh my god. I just said, ‘what's going on this world?’ [...] This is not like a human being. You cannot be happy for others' pain or suffering.” (Resident_Interview_1_W)

3.5 Intra-community diversity

Research question 5.5 – diversity: How did intra-community patterns of difference mediate COVID-19 impacts in the sub-national research sites?

The global COVID-19 pandemic not only brought health challenges but also surfaced deep-seated societal issues. Studies have found that **intra-community diversity can predict COVID-19 indicators** on a sub-municipal level – albeit at different levels and in different ways in different sites (Adhikari et al. 2020; Van Holm et al. 2020; Oluyumi et al. 2021). Higher rates of chronic disease have been reported in ethnic minority populations in several European countries (Modesti et al., 2016), as have higher rates of severe COVID-19 illness and death (Sze et al., 2020; Out et al., 2020). This partially because ethnic minorities are often overrepresented within jobs with high exposure (Sze et al., 2020). Ethnic and religious minorities have also been subject to discrimination and scapegoated as responsible for the spread of COVID-19 (Slaats, 2020; SOS Mitmensch, 2021). Instances have also been reported in which COVID-19-related regulations were enforced in a discriminatory manner (reflecting patterns of law enforcement in general in many countries) (Amnesty International, 2020; Clementi, 2020).

Most CSO representatives interviewed in the ten COVINFORM target sites characterized the neighbourhoods in which they work as **highly diverse**: home to residents with a wide range of ethnic, cultural, linguistic, and socioeconomic backgrounds. Only in a few cases did interviewees describe the sites as homogenous. In specific, CSO interviewees from Austria, Belgium, Germany, Italy, Sweden and Wales reported working in multicultural communities, whereas some interviewees from Greece and Portugal reported working in majority-Greek/Portuguese communities (COVINFORM D6.3, p. 69). CSO representatives made it clear that working in diverse neighbourhoods brought a distinct set of challenges: for example, **adapting response measures to multiple languages and cultures** was a priority for many organisations, and was also indicated as a gap in some sites. Several CSO representatives indicated that discrimination was a problem in their communities prior to the pandemic, and often additionally stated that the pandemic had aggravated this problem in various ways. On the one hand, disruptions to social services increased barriers for vulnerable groups that already suffer from structural discrimination, such as refugees and other migrants. On the other hand, in some sites, ethnic minorities were scapegoated as pandemic multipliers and subject to direct discrimination, up to and including verbal abuse and even physical violence (ibid., p. 71).

The COVINFORM resident interviews validated many of these findings. Due to the fact that the interviews were conducted in the official languages of the target countries, all interviewees were conversational and did not personally experience the same kind of severe language barriers that CSO representatives reported. Nevertheless, many indicated that **language barriers were a problem within their extended social circles** or their neighbourhoods. Moreover, some did indicate that they required **help understanding medical and/or legal terminology**, as was sometimes used in crisis and risk communication or public health guidance.

“There are no opportunities for people that doesn't speak the language [...] For example, my mom, she wants to join some activities and things about wellbeing, but was in some places that don't have an interpreter [...] And for example, if someone doesn't have a person who can help them, they are not able to participate.” (Resident_Interview_5_W)

“I don't speak the language so good. So, it is difficult to watch the news. So, they should add extra subtitles in different languages or something. That would help. Or extra programmes in different languages can also help.” (Resident_Interview_9_BLG)

"I just called my Austrian friends and asked like, 'yes, I saw this but could you please tell me? Because you are reading this, and you understand the details, I just on see the surface meaning of the words but I'm not sure how I should understand it. So, that helps, because sometimes I was not aware and I was like, 'oh, is this still permitted to do?' And my friends were like, 'but did you saw the recent one, it is not allowed,' or 'did you see the recent one, they allowed this and this'." (Resident_Interview_1_AT)

Low-SES women interviewed in the project also shed light on the experiential dimension of COVID-19-related discrimination. Respondents with a migration background in multiple sites reported experiencing **prejudice and blame** due to markers such as visible ethnic difference or culturally specific attire. Some interviewees report indicated that they had experienced discrimination before but that it had worsened during the pandemic, whereas others indicated that they had not had this problem before. At points, ethnic discrimination intersected with the abovementioned social fragmentation based on 'mainstream' vs. 'rejectionist' approaches to COVID-19 discourse and regulations. For example, some interviewees who momentarily could not adhere to guidelines for one reason or another reported that others had racialised this behaviour.

"I feel very sorry because some Spanish people are very racist [...] my Spanish colleagues that I had, oh you, come and take our work, because you have not stayed in your country [...] when I left my country, I arrived, I looked for my family, they asked me, what have you had [...] yes, I was with the virus, I cried, and I said, I'm going to die here." (Resident_Interview_13_ESP)

"People were already very cautious of ethnic minorities [...] when the pandemic came, it has probably just gotten worse." (Resident_Interview_6_W)

"It happens to me sometimes that my son tears the mask off my face and then this little ribbon comes off. Then I can't wear it anymore. Or I lose it on the way to the train, for example. That has also happened to me. Then I was sitting on the train and then I was...I just wear a headscarf. I've been yapped at so many times that I'm a dirty foreigner who doesn't follow the rules because of the mask. And I mean, I don't have to justify myself. I have my reasons why I don't wear a mask, but that's happened to me so many times now. And these are mostly the older people or just really Germans, really German. I was also almost thrown off the train once by two older men [...] It wasn't so bad before, but now it's much worse. People's cohesion has been so broken." (Resident_Interview_12_DE)

A smaller subset of interviewees implied, sometimes in a self-critical tone, that they had noticed people of other ethnicities flouting guidelines. Finally, a few interviewees testified to instances of more severe **inter-ethnic tension** within their neighbourhoods.

"Schönau just has a lot of multiculturalism, so there were also some observations that some... excuse me for saying this, some people didn't give a damn, and some people were very strict about it. I have noticed that. Therefore, I have always said to myself, where I can keep my distance, no matter how." (Resident_Interview_8_DE)

"We have a lot of gypsies. And we are afraid. That's the hardest thing with them and that it's a mess. There are also neat people, but where I live it's very messy [...] It's a place where there's no one left, the gypsies have torn it down, and it's a mess. It is a source of infection. We have nowhere to go. I also announced to the town hall and police [...] One evening at 9 o'clock, they

started a fire, I notified the police and I was afraid that the wind would start and spread the fire.” (Resident_Interview_50_RO)

Socioeconomic inequality was also identified as a significant problem, with a number of interviewees taking explicit account of **economic disparity**. Most interviewees understood the pandemic in clear terms as having had worse effects on those who were already vulnerable, and especially on the poor (though a few interviewees also framed the pandemic as a ‘leveller’, insofar as both the rich and the poor could get sick and die). Interviewees observed that the poor often suffered from food and resource insecurity; that they lived in more confined spaces and in neighbourhoods with fewer resources, worse transportation, and less greenspace; and that they often worked in jobs that were more precarious and more vulnerable to economic fluctuations. They also observed intersections between socioeconomic disadvantage and other factors, such as migration background and gender. Despite their own self-identification as recipients of benefits, many interviewees framed their observations about the unequal impacts of the pandemic as affecting ‘people’ or ‘others in their neighbourhood’, rather than explicitly stating that they were affected. Some respondents who lived in comparatively accommodating living spaces and/or good neighbourhoods positively compared their own circumstances to those of others.

“In the pandemic, not everybody's equal. Because rich people had an easier pandemic and poor people had a really difficult pandemic.” (Resident_Interview_1_W)

“Basically, the majority of people where I live have a migration background, and a majority also belong to vulnerable groups, so yes, that definitely has an influence. That actually made me see what that gap there actually is between the poor and the middle class, and it also showed that while the Coronavirus was actually global, the impact of the coronavirus is not equal. It has a more negative impact on poor people than on rich people.” (Resident_Interview_12_BLG)

“What should I say.. It was as if the city of Babadag was divided in two. On one side there were the poor who had no way to get out, and on the other side there were us, the others, who could go shopping or whatever we could do. But we had relatives, we had friends. And in a way, we were, how do you say? We entered the game, too, because we had to help them. We helped each other, each with what they could.” (Resident_Interview_6_RO)

“Well, look, I've lived in this neighborhood all my life. This neighborhood is a good neighborhood, in the center of the city, not very rich but it is true that here people have less needs than people in other neighborhoods [...] we are lucky that it is not a poor neighborhood, I know that in other neighborhoods in the suburbs and so on, they have had it much worse, because the economic level is maybe a little bit worse than ours. Mine is a very humble house, that I have because I inherited it from my parents.” (Resident_Interview_1_ESP)

Given the diversity of their neighbourhoods, interviewees often observed that **social, cultural and economic differences could lead to different adaptation strategies** in reaction to both the pandemic and response measures. Some indicated how gaps in cultural or linguistic fluency could complicate access to services and/or compliance with regulations or recommended behaviours. Others pointed out how gaps in governmental responses – such as insufficient economic or socio-psychological support – could aggravate the tendency of vulnerable individuals to adopt unhealthy coping strategies, such as drinking or drug use. They also demonstrated clear awareness that health, social, economic, and informational vulnerability are interconnected.

“Older Pontiac Greeks who may not know the language just as well, so there are cultural and language barriers. It was very hard for them to deal with these things.” (Resident_Interview_12_GR)

“Listen, we need a point in the neighbourhood where they do the swabs without charging 15 Euros [...] The poor are poorer and poorer because nobody cares. They also need to offer psychological support, because a lot of people need psychological support. A lot of people started drinking, a lot of old people started drinking. People who never drank. You need reassurance, you need someone who says: 'I'm there'. I did group therapy with other people in San Lorenzo, but now it's a problem to get there, with what the petrol costs, at least 15 Euros round trip.” (Resident_Interview_8_IT)

The pandemic did not merely exacerbate existing differences and tensions, but also gave rise to new ones. As mentioned in the above section on shared attitudes and practices, a number of interviewees observed **fragmentation on the basis of differing COVID-19 attitudes and behaviours**, as well as varying degrees of compliance with response measures. Some spoke about this on a more general societal level, while others testified to clashes within their immediate social circles between those who strictly followed guidelines and those who took a more lax approach.

“I didn't wear a mask, but everyone else wore a mask” (Resident_Interview_1_BLG)

“Well, what I also felt was bad, now, was this compulsory vaccination. My brother and his best friend broke up [over it].” (Resident_Interview_9_AT)

“I stopped seeing people who didn't believe in the virus.” (Resident_Interview_8_IT)

“The [vaccine] opponents, they're more like what I find a thorn in the [...] nobody should force their beliefs or anything on anybody. Because I know someone who said, 'no, vaccinating, that's not possible at all, you're not allowed to do that.' [...] I don't have any contact with that person anymore, because I got vaccinated.” (Resident_Interview_14_DE)

In brief: the COVID-19 pandemic was something unprecedented within the interviewees' lifetimes, and brought numerous longstanding social issues to light, while simultaneously reshaping the fabric of society in new and profound ways. It underscored the fact that decades of economically and socially divisive policy have led to the gradual emergency of parallel societies, in which disparities in access to resources and opportunities are nakedly evident. Generally, it not only revealed, but also aggravated such disparities. In furthermore prompted dramatic (and sometimes arguably draconian) response measures, which required populations to accept significant socioeconomic and socio-psychological trade-offs in the name of preserving the integrity of health systems. This predictably led to bitter divisions.

However, the interviews also revealed another perspective. Throughout this transformative period, not only did challenges become more prominent, but also a heightened sense of gratitude often emerged. A number of interviewees expressed a new appreciation for the things previously taken for granted, such as health, home, family, and social connections. As noted in the above section on joint action, the pandemic also provided an opportunity (based on necessity) to receive and provide support, and make social connections, in previously unforeseen ways.

“I can't say anything negative either because it was a brutal confinement. We were all in the same conditions” (Resident_Interview_3_ESP)

“So, I'm lucky too, there are people who live much worse in much smaller houses and there are seven people living in one room.” (Resident_Interview_1_ESP)

“I think people who don't have any children or no siblings or family, it's even worse. (Resident_Interview_11_DE)

“And neighbors with whom I had never had any contact, who were people, young kids and so on, they did ask me if we needed anything. The people at that time became very good and very supportive. I mean, you noticed that there was something in people that made you think that people are not as bad as they seem. People that I had crossed paths with on the stairs, but I had never spoken to them, they really asked us if we needed anything. That I would tell them thank you very much. And now we're friends and we say hello and those things have changed.” (Resident_Interview_1_ESP)

The spontaneous emergence of new social connections and mutual aid practices during a multidimensional societal crisis – near-simultaneously, in the widest possible spectrum of communities worldwide – provides an unprecedented opportunity for both local policymakers and CSOs. Targeted analysis of quantitative and qualitative data on this phenomenon, gathered in COVINFORM and many other projects, could offer invaluable insight into how and why people self-organise to help one another and themselves under the most challenging of conditions.

4 Lessons learnt

4.1 Lessons learnt on the WP6 research questions

4.1.1 Locations

Research question 5.1 – shared locations: How did spatial system conditions and spatialised practices mediate COVID-19 impacts and responses in the sub-national research sites?

Both prior research and the COVINFORM interviews with CSO representatives and low-SES women indicate that spatial factors and spatialized practices mediated COVID-19 impacts and responses in ways that were diverse and site-specific, but which can be generalised to an extent. One clear pattern was that pre-existing spatialised vulnerabilities, the threat of COVID-19 itself, and the adverse effects of COVID-19 response measures tended to multiply each other in vicious cycles. One concrete example is that dense and insufficient housing conditions not only led to increased rates of transmission, but also exacerbated the negative psychological and social impact of lockdowns (e.g., feelings of confinement, tension with family members). Another example is that neighbourhoods that lacked robust health and educational services also often suffered from insufficient public transportation and digital divides, doubling the burden of accessing such services either in person or online. On the positive side, CSOs placed a focus on intervening in this vicious cycle, for instance by providing in-person or door-to-door material and social support when possible. Moreover, low-SES women themselves actively sought to improve their own wellbeing by pursuing new hobbies, seeking opportunities for contact and solidarity with neighbours, and taking advantage of outdoor spaces such as parks and playgrounds. For many, the pandemic deepened their appreciation of both the people and the communal spaces in their neighbourhoods (even in cases in which the latter were limited).

4.1.2 Social ties

Research question 5.2 – shared social relations: How did social networks mediate COVID-19 impacts in the sub-national research sites?

The role of social ties in mediating COVID-19 impacts and responses appears generalizable across COVINFORM research sites. While prior research indicates that dense social networks could act as vectors for the SARS-CoV-2 virus, they were also essential for socio-psychological wellbeing and the dissemination of material support and information alike. This was especially the case among vulnerable populations with reduced access to – or trust in – formal social welfare systems or other governmental institutions. All interviewees, both CSO representatives and low-SES women, testify that both the pandemic and governmental response measures disrupted social networks, leading to both feelings of isolation and reduced access to material support. These impacts were particularly deleterious when combined with reduced access to formal material and socio-psychological support, either as a result of the restriction of in-person services or the imposition of new barriers. Low-SES women prioritized familiar channels for maintaining social contact: the telephone and SMS/messaging apps, with video calling mostly reserved for virtual group events and work. They also made extensive use of social media throughout the pandemic, including to access and discuss COVID-19 information. Most low-SES women had diverse information repertoires, but some expressed a preference for secondary crisis and risk communication via social media or personal contacts over primary communication by official or traditional media sources, thus raising the spectre of increased exposure to mis- and disinformation. Many interviewees expressed uncertainty as to the credibility of different sources, and some reported

barriers in accessing clear and reliable information (including ‘hard’ barriers like lack of reliable internet access and ‘soft’ barriers like low digital and/or media literacy). While GOs and CSOs in some sites made active efforts to shore up the resilience of social networks and/or leverage social networks more effectively to disseminate high-quality information, these aspects of the pandemic were clearly underestimated in most response strategies.

4.1.3 Joint action

Research question 5.3 – shared activities: What roles have CSOs, grassroots initiatives, and residents played in the provision of health and social services in the sub-national research sites?

CSOs played a significant role in the provision of health, social, and other services in all sub-national research sites, while the roles played by grassroots initiatives and residents themselves varied on a site-by-site basis. Here, the triangulation of multi-perspectival data – from CSO representatives on the one hand and low-SES women on the other – serves a valuable confirmatory function. CSO representatives were universally assured that their organisations filled critical gaps in governmental responses, including by acting to mitigate their negative unintended consequences and trade-offs. Low-SES women confirmed this, mentioning CSOs more often than GOs as frontline providers of support in the health, social, and economic/material domains (though this may be in part because interviewees were unaware of the indirect positive impacts of governmental support schemes that targeted systems rather than individuals). Religious organisations, including both large foundations such as Caritas and local institutions and communities, were especially prominent in many research sites. Low-SES women also testified that mutual aid within their social networks and neighbourhoods also proved invaluable in terms of not only emotional support and practical assistance (e.g., with shopping), but also sometimes with regard to material resources. Grassroots initiatives founded during the pandemic assumed a lower profile in both CSO and resident interviews: only some CSO representatives indicated that they had worked with grassroots initiatives, and likewise, only some low-SES women indicated that they had received support formally organised via such initiatives. However, both CSO representatives and low-SES women testified to the importance of volunteers, and both groups mentioned an upswing in volunteering and a sense of mutual responsibility and solidarity as among the few positive impacts of the pandemic. Governmental responses to future crises could benefit from improved efforts to engage, empower, assess, and publicly recognise non-governmental actors and practices – including established CSOs, novel grassroots initiatives, volunteer programmes, and spontaneous expressions of mutual aid.

4.1.4 Shared attitudes and practices

Research question 5.4 – shared attitudes and practices: How did shared attitudes, beliefs, and practices – including shared trust – mediate COVID-19 impacts in the sub-national research sites?

As expected, shared attitudes, beliefs, and practices mediated COVID-19 impacts in diverse and sometimes exceedingly complex ways. Interviews with both CSO representatives and low-SES women in the COVINFORM research sites added phenomenological depth and complexity to the broad findings that pro-social attitudes and behaviours, social cohesion, and trust in authorities and other individuals are associated with health-protective behaviours and regulatory compliance – whereas low levels of these factors can reduce compliance. The low-SES interviewees fell on a continuum between a ‘mainstream’ subgroup who generally trusted authorities and prioritised information from official and traditional media sources, and a ‘rejectionist’ subgroup who generally distrusted authorities and

prioritised information from alternative sources or their own social circles. A contribution of the qualitative methodology employed is the insight that adherence to ‘mainstream’ behaviours did not always imply trust in ‘mainstream’ institutions, but rather, could stem primarily from pro-social attitudes, social desirability, or simply the inclination to take the path of least resistance. Conversely, ‘rejectionist’ attitudes are seldom rooted in simple distrust of authorities, but more often appear highly differentiated; on a case-by-case basis, they can be driven by combinations of factors as diverse as individual health conditions, experiences of the health system, or observations of others’ experiences, often aggravated by uncertainty as to what information sources to trust. It seems unlikely that classical, one-way communication campaigns could effectively counter such differentiated, highly personal belief complexes. Rather, two-way engagement with the ‘rejecter community’ may be required. Here, insights gained from CSO representatives and the study of participatory practices could provide an impetus for the development of future crisis response plans.

4.1.5 Intra-community diversity

Research question 5.5 – diversity: How did intra-community patterns of difference mediate COVID-19 impacts in the sub-national research sites?

Both CSO and resident interview findings clearly demonstrated the significance of various patterns of difference in mediating COVID-19 impacts and responses alike. Whereas the analysis of quantitative data clearly shows how diversity factors correlate with COVID-19 indicators, as well as how COVID-19 has exacerbated ethnic and socioeconomic inequalities, the qualitative findings at hand provided an emic view on the experience of inequality and discrimination. CSO representatives and low-SES women alike reported instances of discrimination within their often-highly-diverse communities, including scapegoating of minorities as responsible for spreading the virus. At times, this escalated to the level of verbal abuse and even physical violence. Socioeconomic inequality played an equally significant role: most CSO representatives and low-SES women were well aware of the fact that the pandemic’s effects were felt more acutely by the poor. Likewise, not only CSO representatives but also low-SES women often expressed an inherently ‘intersectional’ perspective on vulnerability during the pandemic, citing concrete examples of how ethnicity, nationality, gender, socioeconomic status, and other social differences can result in compounding vulnerabilities under unequal power structures. Finally, the pandemic not only aggravated existing fault lines within society, but provoked new divisions based on varying attitudes and behaviours toward the virus and response measures. At times, this led to conflicts within interviewees’ own social circles. While other interviewees framed the pandemic as a catalyst for new expressions of social solidarity, few expressed confidence that such expressions would maintain momentum on their own. The challenge for governmental policymakers and civil society organisations is to learn from such spontaneous expressions of solidarity and develop short-, mid-, and long-term structural interventions that enable their emergence and augment their sustainability.

4.2 Lessons learnt on risk assessment

COVINFORM D2.3 *Technical report* defines a risk assessment model encompassing threats; physical/health, social, economic, and informational vulnerabilities and consequences; and resilience (e.g., the ability to recover and adapt). The model is operationalised in the COVINFORM risk

assessment dashboard (cf. COVINFORM D2.9), which displays and maps aggregated data² on a range of threats, vulnerabilities, and resilience factors, as well as key COVID-19 outcomes.

Whereas the risk assessment dashboard focuses on country-level conditions, the WP6 research focused on individual testimonials (and, in the case of CSO representatives, organizational activities). These two research directions are strongly complementary. The former, quantitative direction enables the identification and tracking of structural trends; the latter, qualitative direction sheds light on the way these trends were experienced. An additional contribution of the qualitative research is insight into phenomena that country-level quantitative indicators cannot capture, either due to geophysical or temporal scale (e.g., too local, too short-term) or due to gaps in the data collection agendas and methods of statistical institutions (e.g., the failure of most EU countries to disaggregate data by ethnic identity). The following sections review the major dimensions of the risk assessment model from the perspective of the WP6 findings.

4.2.1 Threats

The COVINFORM risk assessment model identifies three categories of threats: the virus, variants of concern, and factors impacting the pandemic's likelihood of development, such as mobility, international trade, migration, housing concentration, pollution, temperature, and the age of the population. CSO representatives and low-SES women interviewed in the project confirmed the salience of all of these threats. They emphasised the relevance of **structural threat multipliers** impacting the pandemic's likelihood of development; specifically, they confirmed the relevance of migration, housing concentration, and age of the population (currently included in the model), while also identifying additional factors such as physical and digital infrastructure, health and school system conditions, public transportation conditions, structuralised socioeconomic precarity, structuralised discrimination, and general poor governance. However, the interviewees also made it clear that these factors tend to vary widely on a location-by-location basis, even on a sub-municipal level; as comparable data on that level is not available, it would be impossible to include them in the current assessment model.

The CSO representative and resident interviewees also drew attention to a range of other threats that they spontaneously associate with COVID-19. **Ancillary threats** mentioned by CSO representatives and low-SES women include mis- and disinformation and those who spread it; abusive individuals whose harmful behaviours are expedited or aggravated by the pandemic (e.g., abusive partners or family members, discriminatory individuals, etc.); state institutions and actors (e.g., harmful laws and regulations, the police); and finally, COVID-19 response measures themselves. In some cases, interviewees assessed these ancillary threat objects as more significant than the virus itself. While it is only logical for a COVID-19 risk assessment model to place primary weight on the threat it is immediately designed for, it would be advisable to take ancillary threats into account as well.

4.2.2 Vulnerabilities and consequences

The risk assessment model identifies four domains of vulnerability: physical, social, economic, and informational. Some of the indicators utilised pertain to characteristics of systems (e.g., number of

² The sources of data used include the European Climate Assessment & Dataset (<https://www.ecad.eu/>), European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (<https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en>), European Sea Ports Organisation (<https://www.espo.be/>), Eurostat (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>), Google Mobility data (<https://www.google.com/covid19/mobility/>), and the WHO - Global Health Observatory (<https://www.who.int/data/gho>).

hospitals, GDP, income inequality, etc.), while others pertain to characteristics of systems and individuals (e.g., prevalence of pre-existing health conditions, education levels, employment levels, percentage living in poverty, etc.). The model assesses COVID-19 consequences in these domains as well, with the addition of environmental consequences. The CSO and resident interviews confirmed the relevance of all of the indicators considered in the model, while also nearly always emphasising that **experiences of vulnerability are multidimensional**. This is shown in the figure below.

Figure 2. Vulnerability across domains (Edwards, 2022)

The interviewees also drew attention to vulnerabilities that are not taken into account – sometimes due to the way categories are defined, and sometimes due to a lack of comparable data collected in all of the target countries. For instance:

With regard to **physical/health vulnerabilities and outcomes**, both CSO and resident interviewees identified a range of vulnerabilities aside from COVID-19 or other diseases: examples are drug addiction, housing and food precarity, etc. Recalling that physical vulnerabilities do not begin and end with disease, much less pandemic disease, is an important lesson learned for risk assessment design.

With regard to **social vulnerabilities and outcomes**, both CSO and resident interviewees placed more emphasis than the model on structural discrimination and social exclusion, based both on ethnic/cultural/national grounds and socioeconomic grounds. They also emphasised the importance of social networks as critical vectors for social support, material support, and information, especially for groups with limited contact with formal social welfare systems. Another theoretical lens through which to view such resource dynamics is social capital. Future risk assessment models could experiment with incorporating indicators on discrimination/exclusion, social network density, and social capital, given the availability of suitable data.

With regard to **economic vulnerabilities and outcomes**, both CSO and resident interviewees stressed the experiential dimension, which encompasses a range of factors other than employment status and income. The type and stability of work, for instance, can factor into perceived socioeconomic status as heavily as the wage received. Structural factors, such as access to public transportation, can also have economic knock-on effects that could be taken into account when assessing overall economic risk. However, again, this would depend upon data availability.

Finally, with regard to **informational vulnerabilities and outcomes**, the emphasis placed by both CSO and resident interviewees on social networks again comes to the fore. For a large number of residents, secondary crisis and risk communication channels are as important, if not more so, than primary channels. Social media is especially predominant. Given its ubiquity, incorporating data on social media use into risk modelling experiments could be productive.

4.2.3 Resilience

The risk assessment model identifies two dimensions of resilience: **ability to recover** (as indicated in the model by the spread of economic activity, emergency investment in health care, investment in vaccines, income support, etc.) and **ability to adapt** (as indicated by investment in rebuilding vulnerable industries, digitisation, innovation, etc.). CSO interviewees testified to the importance of these factors. Resident interviewees, on the other hand, seldom mentioned fiscal policy measures aside from direct income support, which only a few received. The takeaway is that despite their numerous knock-on benefits, fiscal measures that target systems, sectors, and organisations rather than individuals appear largely invisible to vulnerable populations.

Another insight offered by CSO and resident interviewees is that **recovery and adaptation take place on a bottom-up basis as well as a top-down basis**. CSOs proactively worked to enhance the resilience of their target communities; indeed, level of CSO activity and level of GO/CSO coordination could be taken as resilience indicators. Individual low-SES women also demonstrated resilience by seeking new opportunities for social contact and solidarity, working proactively to help themselves and one another recover a sense of wellbeing and normality when possible, and to adapt to the ‘new normal’ when necessary. While data collection on such individual-level activity would undoubtedly prove challenging, proxy variables could include volunteering rates, as well as, where available, usage of mutual aid portals and other online participatory initiatives.

4.3 Lessons learnt on the socio-ecological systems framework

4.3.1 Governance systems

McGinnis & Ostrom (2014) describe governance systems as comprised of **governmental and non-governmental organisations, network structures, property-rights systems, operational-choice rules, collective-choice rules, constitutional-choice rules, and monitoring and sanctioning rules**. Within the context of COVID-19, Ling et al. (2021) identify top-down leadership, restrictions and norms, an emergency response plan, and testing policies as indicators of governance (p. 3).

CSO representatives in the COVINFORM target sites indicated that governmental organisations and non-governmental organisations both played important roles in local COVID-19 responses (cf. COVINFORM D6.4, pp. 18-19). Their assessments of GO performance and impact were highly varied, whereas their assessments of CSO performance and impact were mostly positive. Low-SES women in the target sites mostly echoed this assessment: many were critical of governmental responses on both the national policy level (e.g., lockdown strategies) and the local level of resource provision. Conversely, a number indicated that they had received direct support from CSOs. Here it should be noted that this is not an objective, but rather a subjective assessment: the interviewees seemed largely unaware of the indirect impacts of governmental support initiatives that targeted systems, sectors, or organisations, as opposed to those that directly benefitted individuals.

Governance aspects also come into play when interpreting interviewees' assessments of their own living conditions. Many described both their personal living conditions and the physical and digital infrastructural conditions in their neighbourhoods as insufficient. These insufficiencies caused concrete harm: for instance, housing density increased both COVID-19 transmission rates and the subjective fear of infection, while poor physical and digital infrastructure multiplied the harmful impacts of contact restrictions. Such conditions are, of course, the outcomes of long-running governance processes and priorities – and, in broader historical perspective, of structural inequalities in the world system itself. Here, combining intersectionality and socio-ecological systems analysis could contribute to the development of both theoretical frameworks.

4.3.2 Resource systems and units

According to McGinnis & Ostrom (2014), resource systems are defined by variables such as **sector, clarity of system boundaries, size of resource system, productivity of system, equilibrium properties, and predictability of system dynamics**, whereas resource units are defined by variables such as **resource unit mobility, growth/replacement rate, interaction between resource units**, etc. Within the context of COVID-19, Ling et al. (2021) identify the indicators of high facility adequacy, high technology availability, and high economic performance (p. 3).

Both CSO and resident interviewees confirmed the multiplicity of resource systems that must be taken into account in the analysis of crisis such as the COVID-19 pandemic: not only public health systems, but also child and youth service systems, cultural ecosystems, education systems, housing systems, immigration systems, labour systems, long-term care systems, social welfare systems, women's service systems, etc. Issues that arose across these systems included varying abilities to digitalise services, varying abilities to implement hygiene measures and retain on-site services, limited contact with target groups, gaps in target group trust, funding and HR shortages, and highly varied degrees of contact and coordination between authorities and CSOs.

Both interview target groups – but residents in particular – furthermore confirmed the importance of social networks as resource systems. Especially for vulnerable individuals and groups with low exposure to formal social welfare systems, social networks served as critical vectors for the provision of both socio-psychological and material aid. In some cases, they also served as the primary channels for crisis and risk communication: on the one hand, this filled information gaps, but on the other hand, it heightened exposure to mis- and disinformation and contributed to informational oversaturation. Recognising social networks as resource systems – and social capital as a category of 'resource unit' – could inform policies aimed at enhancing crisis resilience from the bottom up.

4.3.3 Actor systems

McGinnis & Ostrom (2014) describe actor systems as defined by the **number of relevant actors and their socioeconomic attributes, histories/past experiences, and locations**; as well as **leadership and entrepreneurship, norms, knowledge, and resource dependence**. In the COVID-19 context, Ling et al. (2021) suggest the indicators of low population density, high social homogeneity, high trust in government and trust in others, sufficient management knowledge and experience, and effective migration management (p. 3).

CSO and resident interviewees confirmed the multiplicity and diversity of actor systems in the research sites, as well as the contribution of numerous, sometimes-overlooked actors to COVID-19 responses. As mentioned above under 'governance systems', CSOs played an important and highly visible role in

all of the target sites. Often more so than governmental organisations, they were perceived by residents as leaders in responses on a local level. With regard to residents themselves, the interviews revealed a wide range of socio-economic attributes, personal and collective histories, lived experiences, norms, and ways of understanding. It would be challenging to summarise these factors systematically, let alone quantify them. However, it would be irresponsible to fail to take these factors into account when planning a crisis response.

Accordingly, during pre-crisis phases, qualitative research with both residents and organisations in direct contact with residents should be given a high priority alongside quantitative data collection. Such research can contribute critical insight on the lived experiences of vulnerable groups, which quantitative indicators based on aggregated data cannot capture. Formal and informal dialogue mechanisms should also be established to enable the full range of actors within a given geophysical system (municipality, neighbourhood, etc.) to contribute insights, ask questions, and offer recommendations in real-time. During crises, these mechanisms should be activated. Such mechanisms could act not only as data collection channels, but also as a live and public demonstration of participatory, transparent, and accountable governance.

4.3.4 Action situations (interactions and outcomes)

McGinnis & Ostrom (2014) define “action situations” as complex interactions in which “actors in positions make choices among available options in light of information about the likely actions of other participants and the benefits and costs of potential outcomes”. Relevant actions cited include **resource use, information sharing, deliberation processes, conflicts, investment activities, lobbying activities, self-organising activities, networking activities, monitoring activities, and evaluative activities**. Ling et al. (2021) draw on quantitative indices to represent a range of COVID-19-related interactions: e.g., the Stringency Index, Health and Containment Index, and Economic Support Index (p. 3). The outcomes of chains of such actions can be assessed using **social performance measures** and **ecological performance measures**. Here, attention is due to interactive properties of complex adaptive systems, such as multidimensionality, cascading effects, network effects, and the extreme difficulty of predicting certain kinds of outcomes (Edwards, 2022, pp. 6-12; cf. COVINFORM D6.4).

As with the “Actor systems” domain, the CSO representative and resident interviews provided in-depth perspective on the complexity and range of action situations (interactions and outcomes) that unfolded during the pandemic within the research sites. All five of the dimensions of community – location, social ties, joint action, shared attitudes and practices, and intra-community diversity – had clearly identifiable impacts on actors’ assessments of costs and benefits, choices, and experienced outcomes. Locations and their characteristics, for instance, enabled and/or constrained both CSOs’ and individuals’ access to and use of material and digital resources (see Section 4.1.1). Social networks had a determinative impact on information sharing and deliberation processes based on the information shared (e.g., whether to vaccinate) (see Section 4.1.2). Joint actions emerged as the result of self-organising activities among residents, as well as networking activities among CSOs and other actors (see Section 4.1.3). Shared attitudes and practices emerged within and across social networks, in part as a result of information sharing; the emergence of opposing clusters of attitudes and practices led to conflicts, both within the population and with authorities (see Section 4.1.4). Finally, the complexity of all of these coexistent interactions often underscored differences within populations, often aggravating pre-existing inequalities and patterns of discrimination (see Section 4.1.5).

5 Conclusions

The present deliverable synthesizes the findings in work package 6, focused on citizen and community responses. Triangulating desk research, interviews with CSO representatives, and interviews with low-SES women, it addresses the work-package-specific research questions developed in prior deliverables. Lessons learned are then provided with reference to the COVINFORM risk assessment model (developed in work package 2) and the social-ecological systems framework (used in work package 3).

Based on these lessons learned, recommendations for policy and practice are developed in white papers and other project outputs, which are summarised in D8.5.

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